

Effect of Tax Morale on Personal Income Tax Compliance in Edo State

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Abstract

This study was set to investigate the effect of tax morale on personal income tax compliance in Edo State. It became imperative to carry out this study following the series of quests to observe the influence of tax morale on personal income tax compliance in Edo State, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted in carrying out the research. The primary source of data was collected through a questionnaire and used for the study. Tables and percentages were used to analyse the data, while Pearson Chi-Squares estimation technique was adopted to test the hypothesis. Findings obtained showed that infrastructural development has a negative but insignificant influence on personal income tax compliance, while transparency and accountability and taxpayers' awareness have a positive and significant relationship with personal income tax compliance. The study, thus, concludes that only transparency and accountability tend to ensure compliance with personal income tax. At the same time, infrastructural development is not good predictor of personal income tax compliance in Edo State, Nigeria. This, study, thus recommends that government should be more accountable to its citizens to lure them to be tax compliant so that the government can generate enough revenue to perform its fundamental obligations/services equitably to the citizens.

Keywords: Tax morale, tax compliance, infrastructural development, transparency and accountability and taxpayers' awareness

Introduction

Taxation is a vital instrument used by the government in both advanced and developing countries for the achievement of its fiscal policy strategy (Mayowan, 2019). The government needs financial resources to act and discharge its constitutional responsibilities to the public. Tax revenue is one major income source (Chodorow,

2008) that tends to boost the government's income level for the provision of fundamental human needs. With these tax collections, government tends to discharge its constitutional responsibilities to the public, such as quality education, roads, potable water, adequate security, and to meet societal expectations and well-being. One of the constitutional

responsibilities of the government to its citizens is the stabilisation of the economy by ensuring adequate income redistribution, which is the hallmark of taxation which can only be guaranteed when there is adequate compliance to tax laws and administration by tax payers on the whole.

A major challenge for decision-makers in a growing economy is ensuring that the majority of taxpayers pay their taxes due to a low level of awareness (Akan and Oditia, 2013). Compliance with tax payment is not only adhered to as a result of the possibility of detection, tax rates, and enforcement but also on the taxpayer's part not to resist payment of taxes. Consistent with this, people act with integrity and in an honest manner, present accurate information and enhance the extent of their willingness to pay tax as a result of the intrinsic motivation for tax payment known as tax morale (Alm and Togler, 2006). Tax morale measures the desire of individuals to pay taxes or the belief that paying taxes gives them the enablement to contribute their quota to society. Thus, tax morale is a hidden motivation to pay taxes, and it is directly associated with obeying tax laws which is a noticeable action (Akan and Oditia, 2013; Alm, 2018; Fadi, Martin, and Roberta, 2016). However, low tax morale culminates in low tax compliance levels, which thus impedes development, specifically in the area of economic growth. Tax morality has many determinants, which include but are not limited to: socio-demographics [age, gender, education]; socio-economic [marriage status, employment, economic situation, and religiosity]; trust [toward the government, legal system, judiciary,

president, civil servants]; political participation [direct democracy, local autonomy]; tax policy [prevention factors, tax systems, tax administration, perception of taxpayers]; and culture [culture of society] (Jackson and Milliron, 1986).

The study of personal tax compliance demands that factors (such as infrastructural development, transparency and accountability which enhance tax compliance position and actions of the tax payers are of significant interest that must be studied. Efforts to expand the tax base depend on the way taxpayers see the tax administration and enforcement and whether there is transparency and accountability in the process.

The main objective of the study is to find out the effect of tax morale on complying with the payment of personal income tax in Edo State, Nigeria. The study will focus on how government infrastructural development and transparency in governance affect the morale of taxpayers leading to tax compliance by individuals. The hypotheses of the study are also drawn from the objectives.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Tax

Tax is one major avenue through which government at all levels generate revenue (Mayowan, 2019). The tax system enables the government to generate tax revenue required to discharge its fundamental responsibilities, which, in no doubt, ensures economic growth and development (Alabede, Arifini, and Idris,

2011; Ali, Fjeldstad, and Sjursten, 2014; Fadi *et al.*, 2016). According to Anyaduba (2000), tax is a compulsory levy on the income generated by individuals and corporate organisations by agencies of the government for the purpose of generating revenue. Appah and Oyandonghan (2011) see tax as a levy imposed on an individual or on his property by the government to enable them to meet the basic need of society.

Personal Income Tax Compliance

James and Alley (2002) defined tax compliance as the willingness of the taxpayer to pay his or her tax without any form of enforcement. It also means declaring all your income in accordance with tax laws or regulations and obeying court judgement in that regard. It is the act of filling your returns as and when due, openly declaring your income and paying all the necessary taxes as raised by the tax authority. Tax compliance is the willingness of taxpayers to obey tax laws and balance the economic equilibrium of the country. According to (Noor, Jeyapalan, and Uchenna, 2014), tax compliance is transparently reporting all your income and expenses and making necessary claims in accordance with tax laws.

To this end, the studies of (Anyaduba, Eragbhe, and Kennedy, 2012; Devos, 2012) on tax compliance documented many factors, such as deterrent, socio-psychological, fiscal exchange and comparative treatment, determine individual compliance resolution of tax payment or not. More so, individual compliance behaviour is arguably different among countries as well as individuals. Tax compliance is, to a large extent, influenced by fourteen variables which include:

age, sex, literacy, and income level, income sources, residence, peer influence, ethics, honesty, complexity, and contact of tax agencies, penalty, measurable possibility, and tax level. In relation to tax compliance measurement, a prior study in India provided a tax compliance index as an aggregate index where tax compliance is a measure of actual income tax generated compared to the amount of taxes that government suppose to collect.

Tax Morale

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) defines tax morale as the 'intrinsic willingness to pay tax'. It further defines this intrinsic motivation in its consultation document what is driving tax morale? as 'our understanding of what motivates taxpayers to participate in, and comply with, the tax system'. It regards this as 'a vital aspect of the tax system, as most tax systems rely on the voluntary compliance of taxpayers for the bulk of their revenues'. Tax morale is about far more than an individual's moral beliefs; it also includes their actions, which may well not reflect those professed beliefs.

According to Akan and Odita (2013), tax morale as a concept is credited to Schmolders (1960), who sees it as the mind-set of a group or groups of taxpayers about the achievement or abandonment of their tax obligations based on their tax awareness is the hallmark of the sovereignty of the state. The issue of morale in tax began to elicit interest among researchers in the 1990s and concerted efforts have been geared towards examining the fundamental question of

tax compliance despite the low level of fines, penalties as well as possibility of being audited as studies have revealed based on the need assessment, early theories suggest lesser tax compliance. Based on previous research work, new studies have been carried out to find new issues that affect tax morale.

The first research on tax morale was carried out by German scholars who confirmed that the early motive of tax morale is the reason why people do not cheat. In developing nations such as Nigeria, the level of exposure to non-compliance and punishment is so low, and despite this, taxpayers are still rational and sensitive to compliance with tax payments. Thus, morale in tax is defined as the enthusiasm of paying taxes, and it is closely related to compliance with tax laws. Many taxpayers want to see the reason for paying taxes translated into infrastructural development. Questions like what do government do with all these taxes they are collecting from us? They see infrastructure as the government's judicious use of their tax money.

Infrastructural Development

Infrastructures are essential to improving the economy of any nation and are characterized as social goods (Afuberoh and Okoye, 2014; Olabisi, Afolabi, Olagunju, and Madariola, 2020). The concept is made up of the Latin prefix *infra* (which means beneath) and *structure*. Infrastructure is defined as making available basic amenities to the corporate world and individual homes in society. There are two types of infrastructures: hard infrastructures (these are huge substantial networks required to ensure a

functional and modernized industrial nation) and soft infrastructures (these are institutions necessary to sustain the basic social needs of a country, for example, all the system relating to finance, education, healthcare and government as well as emergency services) (Adesoji and Chike, 2013; **Olabisi et al., 2020**).

Investment in infrastructural development is fundamental in ensuring a developed economy as it solves probable economic growth. On average, infrastructural resources are capital intensive, involve huge capital outlay, long-term assets, site and use specific, and are competitive in nature (Adesoji and Chike, 2013; **Olabisi et al., 2020**; **Umar et al., 2018**). Infrastructural development is also the total amenities and social facilities made available by the government to increase the living standard of the people. Consequently, these infrastructural developments include pipe-borne water, good roads, good educational facilities, good and adequate health care centres, qualified teachers and teaching facilities (Adesoji and Chike, 2013; Anyaduba and Aronmwan, 2015; **Olabisi et al., 2020**). To this end, the fundamental economic objective of emerging nations is to enhance the rate of economic growth as well as income per head which tends to ensure high living standard which can only be ensure in a high tax compliance environment.

Infrastructural development has become an issue that affect the tax morale of citizens as they always question what tangible thing they can see that government has done with the taxes they pay.

Transparency and Accountability

Accountability means giving account of ones stewardship of what is entrusted in your care. It has do with maintaining openness in character and conducts in doing government business. It is transparently complying with rules, norms and guidelines in conducting government business.

Accountability involves individual or government agencies providing the valuable and correct information about their activities and justifying their action with supportive evidence to avoid sanctions. Accountability provides an answer for actions and provides the mechanism for enforcement of legal and regulatory frameworks.

Accountability provides the basis for tax compliance, but where government fails to give account of taxes collected in the form of the provision of infrastructure and other benefits, it will definitely affect the level of tax compliance. Tax morale is the hidden motivation that compels tax payers to provide correct information that will aid voluntary tax compliance. The extent to which government displays accountability will shape the tax morale of the citizens and in turn affect the level of their compliance in the voluntary payment of taxes. This forms the basis of social contracts between the government and taxpayers (Sitardja and Dwimulyani, 2016).

International Monetary Fund (IMF) and World bank have always promoted accountability among various arms of government that have dealing with them. Omolehinwa and Naiyeju (2015) emphasized that lack of accountability has been a problem among developing nations of the world when it comes to tax compliance and

provision of basic goods. Igbeng, Beredugo, and Adu (2015) stated that despite the fact that tax revenue increased between 2012 and 2014 in Nigeria which ought to lead to increase in development, the country rather deteriorated in infrastructural development and was ranked among the poorest nations of the world.

Penalties for Non-Payment of Tax by Tax Payers

The penalties attached to non-compliance in tax law differ from country to country. Various penalties are attached to varied offences in tax law. A particular penalty depends on the level of evasion committed by the tax payer. For instance, the penalty for late filling of returns differs from non-filling or falsification of accounting records or even refusal to keep proper records. Deliberate evasion of tax attracts stiffer penalties than non-deliberate tax evasion. It is yet to be proved if there is a relationship as regards the effect of the penalty on the tax compliance behaviour of citizens.

Tax compliance reacts more positively to fine than as it does to other measures to enforce compliance. Compliance rises as fine increases but not with audit probabilities. Other researches have reported that tax compliance does not have a relationship with penalties and fines. In some climes, fine can be seen as a de-motivator when it comes to tax compliance as it is perceived to be harmful to the community.

Empirical Review

Siahaan (2013) examined the effect of tax openness and trust on tax payers' willingness to

comply with tax laws in Indonesia using the path analytic regression techniques, and the result showed a positive but insignificant relationship between tax transparency and voluntary compliance with tax laws. The result also showed that tax openness through having trust in governance had a positive and significant influence on compliance with tax laws

Rasak and Adefula (2013) examined taxpayer's attitudes and how it affected the decision on tax compliance in Tamale, Ghana, using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique and discovered that the majority of citizens do not regard transparency and accountability in governance which in turn have a negative effect on individual tax compliance. The study concludes that tax payers do not have trust in governance and, as such, affect their tax compliance.

Fadjar (2013) studied how direct and indirect tax compliance affects voluntary tax compliance in Indonesia using the OLS regression technique. Tax payers in service industries were sampled in the study. The result found that direct tax transparency had an insignificant effect on voluntary tax compliance, while indirect tax transparency was positive and significant on voluntary tax compliance through trust.

Kiow, Salleh, and Kassim (2017) studied the determinants of personal tax compliance by individuals in Peninsular Malaysia. Findings revealed that the majority of the tax payers compliance is their ethical perception and the level of transparency displayed in government activities. The study concluded that individual perception of how the government uses revenue

generated from tax for the benefit of its citizens determines to a large extent, the level of their tax compliance. Transparency has to do with how the government is using its tax revenue to provide its citizens with basic needs and amenities that would influence tax payers decisions as regards tax compliance.

Sitardja and Dwimulyani (2016) studied how trust and good governance influenced tax compliance among public companies listed in Indonesian Stock Exchange using a questionnaire employing the structural equation model with partial least squares. The outcome is a positive relationship between fairness, trust, transparency and tax compliance.

Orunmwense and Aiwoho (2021) examined the determinants of tax morale and tax compliance in Nigeria. The study's objectives are trusted in government, culture, age, religion, education, and employment. The study adopted a cross-sectional research survey design as a method of investigation. Four (4) public limited companies listed under the Nigeria stock exchange formed the basis upon which the investigation was carried out and the sample size obtained for the study. A questionnaire was used as a research instrument to elicit responses, a total of three hundred and eighty-two (382) questionnaire copies were administered, and all three hundred and eighty-two copies were retrieved. Multiple regressions were used to analyse the data. The study revealed that trust in government, employment, religion, and age significantly correlate with tax morale and compliance. In contrast, culture and education have an insignificant relationship with tax

morale and tax compliance in Nigeria. The study recommends that understanding a taxpayer's social psychological (demographic) as it relates to tax morale would help address the issue of tax compliance in Nigeria, and this would also help the government formulate better policies in tax-related matters.

Okanlawon, Raji, Bojuwon and Kafayat (2022) examined the impact of tax morale on the economic development of Nigeria using Lagos state as a case study. A cross-sectional survey was used with a questionnaire as the significant tool for data collection. Simple tables and percentages were used to analyse the data, while regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis. The result shows that there is a significant positive correlation between tax morale and economic development. The study recommends that government should embark on programmes that will win trust in governance and positively impacts on tax morale of its citizenry.

Theoretical Framework

Economic Deterrent Theory: This research is based on Economic Deterrent Theory because it captures all tax morale determinants and tax compliance. This theory, which is premised on the economic theory of obeying the law, commonly focuses on deterrence. Deterrence can be attained through the punitive approach and the persuasive approach. The economist views tax compliance as the rational behaviour of taxpayers who sees themselves as having a moral judgment that does not take risk and who enjoys tax evasion if the benefit of evading tax outweighs the costs (Mayowan, 2019). This theory was first revealed

in the 60s from the study of Becker, who investigated illicit action employing an economic blueprint. Becker put forward a slight view which suggested that deterrents such as the possibility of discovery, penalties and fines are factors that are under the influence of society. In line with Becker's argument, this theory presupposes that behaviour is subjective to factors like tax rate (which determines the gain from evading tax), punishment for fraud and possibility of exposure (which determines costs).

This theory literarily considers an individual as a rational and reasonable being who weighs the pros and cons of evading taxes and thus ignores payment of tax if the perceived gain of non-payment exceeds the costs (Walsh, 2012). The postulation deals with logical and reasonable choice under improbability as to whether nonpayment of tax is beneficial or adversely consequential to the taxpayer (Fjeldstad, Schulze, and Sjursen, 2012). The proposition of this theory is that there tends to be a high level of tax evasion when the punishment for deviants are low, while fewer people tend to evade taxes with high punishment measures (Fjeldstad *et al.*, 2012). Consistent with this, the proponents advocate a stricter assessment and grave punishments for defaulters as a way of decreasing non-payment of taxes. This theory has its limitation because it was based on assumption and was later modified by Allingham and Sandmo in the 1970s by working out a theory that includes the assumption that taxpayers benefit from the knowledge of the punishment given to tax evaders.

Intrinsic Motivation Theory: Intrinsic motivation depends on the application of policy instruments. Frey (1997) claims that tax morale is not expected to be crowded out if honest taxpayers perceive the stricter policy to be directed against dishonest taxpayers. Regulations which prevent free-riding by others and establish fairness and equity help preserve tax morale. If intrinsic motivation is not recognized, taxpayers get the feeling that they can as well be opportunistic. This considers the relevance of policy instruments in supporting or damaging intrinsic motivation.

Theory of Crime: The deterrence doctrine can be traced back to the classical works of Jeremy, Bentham and Cesare (Murphy, 2008). Their classical utilization theory of crime is that people are rational actors who behave in a manner that will maximize their expected utility. Becker (1968) argued that authorities needed to appropriately balance between detection of non-compliers and sanctions to the point where non-compliance becomes irrational. They began to focus their attention on researching compliance rather than deterrence and realised the importance of persuasion and cooperation as regulatory tools for gaining compliance. In fact, research has shown that the use of threat and legal coercion, particularly when perceived as illegitimate, can produce negative behavior; these actions are more likely to result in further non-compliance (Murphy and Harris, 2007).

Methodology

The research adopted the survey research design which is one of the most important designs

utilised in management sciences. The data were primarily sourced, which means that the data were obtained by conducting and administering the questionnaire. Since the population of self-employed individuals in Edo State is very large and cannot easily be determined, Cochran (1977) formula for determining sample size in an infinite population was used determining the sample size:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 PQ}{e^2}$$

Where: n = sample size; Z = the Z-value gotten from the Z-table; $Q = 1 - P$; P = Estimated proportion of the population assumed to be 50% (i.e. 0.50); and e = The margin error limit stated at 5%. Assigning values to these symbols, the sample size is calculated thus:

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{(0.05)^2} \\ n &= \frac{3.8416 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{0.0025} \\ n &= \frac{0.9604}{0.0025} \\ n &= 384 \end{aligned}$$

The total sample is given as 384 and the questionnaire was distributed among the three hundred and eighty-four (384) self-employed individuals/respondents in selected Local Governments from Edo State, Nigeria and 300 respondents returned their copies of the questionnaire.

The scale rating range from (1), indicating the lowest evaluation of a particular construct to (5), indicating a full assessment of each

component of the observed variables (infrastructural development, and transparency and accountability). The questionnaire comprised of seven (4) sections, some of which include: the introductory letter, the biodata, infrastructural development data, and transparency and accountability data. The questionnaire was strategically designed, and a sample test was carried out on every question to ascertain its validity. The questionnaire was made easy for the

respondents to select from the option which, to them, best suits the question asked. Cronbach Alpha technique was used to test the validity and reliability of the questionnaire and the result indicated is 0.84 which is a good result.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 summarize the percentages of responses from individuals to the options available for the questions under each category;

Table 1: Infrastructural Development

S/N	Question: Infrastructural Development	SA	A	SD	D	U
1.	Self-employed individual who are resident in areas where there are good roads comply more to tax payments.	63 (21%)	66 (22%)	114 (42%)	21 (7%)	24 (8%)
2.	Self-employed individuals residing in areas of constant electricity have increased tax morale which will impact positively on tax compliance.	36 (12%)	48 (16%)	147 (49%)	39 (13%)	30 (10%)
3.	Entrepreneur in local government with no infrastructural development will completely evade tax.	36 (12%)	39 (13%)	186 (62%)	27 (9%)	9 (3%)
4.	Entrepreneurs who are resident in areas where there are no constant electricity and good road will most likely understate income so as to reduce tax liability due to low tax morale.	30 (10%)	36 (12%)	69 (23%)	126 (47%)	24 (8%)

Source: Researcher's compilation (2022)

From Table 1, on responses relating to the effects of tax morale on infrastructural development in Edo State showed that 42% of the respondents strongly disagreed that areas with more good roads comply more to tax payment in Edo State yearly, 49% strongly disagreed that tax payers that enjoy electricity comply more to payment of taxes, 62% strongly disagreed that

entrepreneur that enjoy not government infrastructure will completely evade tax, and 47% disagreed that individuals that do not enjoy basic infrastructures will not declare their income to reduce tax liability. This implies that infrastructural development does not play significant role in tax compliance in Edo State.

Table 2: Transparency and Accountability

S/N	QUESTION: Transparency and Accountability in Governance	SA	A	SD	D	U
1.	Government disclosure of revenue collected will improve tax payers' compliance behaviour.	117 (39%)	102 (34%)	36 (12%)	12 (4%)	30 (10%)
2.	Trust in tax collection and administration will increase tax compliance behaviour.	63 (21%)	39 (13%)	33 (11%)	138 (46%)	27 (9%)
3.	Transparency of tax administration or tax authority is key to driving compliance.	138 (46%)	63 (21%)	0 (0%)	66 (22%)	33 (11%)
4.	Absence of corruption among tax officials will enhance compliance.	51 (17%)	129 (43%)	27 (9%)	42 (14%)	51 (17%)

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2022)

Data presented in Table 2 showed the responses on the effects of transparency and accountability on tax compliance in Edo State. It was observed that 39% of the respondents strongly agreed that government disclosure of their revenue collection would improve tax compliance, 46% strongly disagreed that the issue of trust in governance would increase tax compliance, 46% strongly agreed that transparency in tax administration will drive tax compliance, and 43% agreed that absence of corruption among tax officials increases tax compliance. This implies that transparency and

accountability affect tax compliance in Edo State.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypotheses designed earlier in the introduction were tested in this section. The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis (H_0) if the calculated P-value is greater than the critical P-value, which stood at 5% level of significance (0.05), otherwise, we reject. The following tables present the Pearson's chi-square test results analyzing the various research questions outlined for this study.

Table 3: Result of Infrastructural Development and Personal Income Tax Compliance

	Value	d.f.	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.550 ^a	1	.458		
Continuity Correction ^b	.317	1	.573		
Likelihood Ratio	.554	1	.457		
Fisher's Exact Test				.483	.288
Linear-by-Linear Association	.548	1	.459		
N of Valid Cases	383				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 16.08.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

The result of Pearson's chi-square test of independence between infrastructural development and personal income tax compliance (PITC) is presented in Table 3. The Pearson Chi-Square

value of 0.550 with a degree of freedom (d.f.) of 1 and probability value 0.458 suggests that there is no significant relationship between infrastructural development and personal income tax compliance.

Table 4: Result of Transparency and Accountability and Personal Income Tax Compliance

	Value	d.f.	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.656 ^a	1	.017		
Continuity Correction ^b	3.949	1	.047		
Likelihood Ratio	4.288	1	.038		
Fisher's Exact Test				.034	.034
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.641	1	.018		
N of Valid Cases	383				

a. 1 cells (25.0%) have an expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.96.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

The result of the Pearson's chi-square test of independence between transparency and accountability and personal income tax compliance (PITC) is presented in Table 4. The Pearson chi-square value of 5.656 with a degree of freedom (d.f.) of 1 and related probability value of 0.017 shows that there a significant relationship between transparency and accountability and Personal Income Tax Compliance.

Hypothesis One

- i. There is no significant relationship between infrastructural development and personal income tax compliance.
- ii. **Test Statistic and Decision:** The Pearson Chi-Square value of 0.550 with a probability value 0.458 is greater than 5% level of significance. The study concludes that ID has

no significant relationship with PITC. Thus the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between infrastructural development and personal income tax compliance was accepted.

Hypothesis Two

- i. There is no significant relationship between transparency and accountability and personal income tax compliance.
- ii. **Test Statistic and Decision:** The Pearson chi-square value of 5.656 with and the related probability value of 0.017 was less than 5% level of significance. The study, therefore, concludes that transparency and accountability has a significant relationship with PITC. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between transparency and accountability and

personal income tax compliance was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Infrastructural development (ID) reveals an insignificant relationship with personal income tax compliance (PITC), which is inconsistent with the economic deterrent theory. This indicates that irrespective of increases in infrastructural development, and self-employed individuals are still not motivated to comply with prompt tax payment in the long-run. Following from the research finding, infrastructural development has a Pearson Chi-Square coefficient of 0.550 with an associated probability value of 0.458 greater than 5% level of significance. The result suggests that ID does not significantly influence PITC. This, of course, is attributable to corruption, unfavourable government actions in the past in terms of mismanagement of public funds, tribalism and nepotism, cronyism, as well as empty promises towards the people, which is prevalent in the Nigerian governance process.

Transparency and accountability (TRA) were found to have a significant relationship with PITC when measured at a 5% level of significance. Following the research finding, TRA has a Pearson Chi-Square coefficient of 5.656 with a probability value of 0.017, less than a 5% level of significance. The result suggests that TRA significantly influences PITC, and this is consistent with the prior expectation. This, of course, suggests that transparency and accountability on the part of the tax Authority as well as government officials invariably will result

in high PITC. That is, transparency and accountability by the government on how government resources were applied in providing basic amenities will enhance personal income tax compliance. This finding aligns with the finding of Kiow, Salleh, and Kassim (2017), Sitardja and Dwimulyani (2016) but inconsistent with the findings of Fadjar (2013), Rasak and Adefula (2013), and Siahaan (2013).

Conclusion

The broad aim of the research is to investigate the impact of tax morale on personal income tax compliance in Edo State. Tax morale is measured by the perception of taxpayers in what the government do with their taxes in the area of infrastructural development and their perception of how government render an account of their stewardship to the populace. Specifically, personal income tax compliance is a topical issue which will continue to attract attention in the Nigerian economy due to the wide income disparity between the have and have not. Also, economic deterrent, socio-psychology, and comparative treatment theories have shown the significance of PITC for the interest of all stakeholders (self-employed tax payers). Following the various reviews, results of analysis, interpretations and hypotheses tested, the outcome of the research showed that transparency and accountability have a positive and significant relationship with Personal Income Tax compliance. In contrast, Infrastructural Development has a negative but insignificant relationship with Personal Income Tax compliance at a 5% critical level. Following

the empirical findings, the study can conclude transparency and accountability tend to increase PITC in Edo State, while Infrastructural Development is not a good predictor of Personal Income Tax compliance in Edo State.

Recommendations

Having investigated the impact of tax morale, such as infrastructural development, transparency and accountability on personal income tax compliance (PITC) in Edo State, the study recommends that government always make open how it spends taxpayers' money so that personal income tax compliance and collection, especially among individuals in self-employment in Edo State, will increase. Also, a tax system aimed at higher tax incidence on the rich via their tax base, such as the opulence tax, should be initiated. This is to enable the government to spread income by taking money from the haves (in the form of tax revenue) to provide for the poor in society.

The study finding that infrastructural development does not play a significant role in personal income tax compliance implies that Edo State Government should place less emphasis on using basic infrastructure to influence the tax morale of taxpayers.

This study contributed to knowledge by looking at other factors that can influence the tax morale of individuals, which is a shift from other studies that usually use culture, religion, age and education.

It is also recommended that further study in the tax morale should look at how trust in governance and mode of enforcement of tax laws

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